

Bisbenzimidazole diamide copper(II) complexes and their reactivity towards superoxide^ψ

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Manuscript received 6 June 2005

A benzimidazole-based diamide ligand *N,N*-bis(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)propane diamide (GBMA) and *N,N*-bis(*N*-ethyl-2-benzimidazolylmethyl)hexane diamide (E-GBHA) have been synthesized and utilized to prepare copper(II) complexes of general composition [Cu(L)X]X, where X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SCN⁻ and L = GBMA, E-GBHA. The EPR spectra reveal the presence of distorted tetragonal copper site in the complexes with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$. The complexes display a quasi-reversible redox wave due to the Cu^{II}/Cu^I redox couple with $E_{1/2}$ varying in the order Cl⁻ < NO₃⁻ ≅ SCN⁻. The copper(II) complexes react by quenching of superoxide radical generated electrochemically.

The development of new and efficient catalysts that mimic the functional properties of copper containing metalloenzyme's with emphasis on oxygenase¹ activity has generated interest both from economic and environmental² point of view. Copper-Zinc Superoxide Dismutase is a dimeric protein, which catalyses the dismutation of superoxide O₂⁻ to dioxygen and hydrogenperoxide, thereby protecting the tissue against oxidative damage³. We have initiated a investigation utilizing diamide bisbenzimidazole based ligands as potential functional model's for superoxide dismutase. The present series of copper(II) complexes generated with GBMA and E-GBHA are being reported for the first time.

Results and discussion

Electronic spectroscopy, ¹H NMR and IR spectral properties :

The absorbance spectra of all the copper(II) complexes were measured in DMSO : CH₃CN (2 : 8) solvent system. UV bands in the range of 271–286 nm are observed for all the complexes and that have been assigned to π-π* transition of benzimidazole group with respect to the parent ligand⁴. An enhancement or decrease in absorption is observed as indicated by their extinction coefficients.

All the complexes exhibit a single symmetrical but broad *d-d* band in the range 670–800 nm characteristics of tetragonal geometry. In general these bands are assigned to the overlapping transition $d_{xz,yz} \rightarrow d_{x,y}$ and d_{xy}

$\rightarrow d_{x,y}$. The decrease in energy of the absorption maxima generally follows the order NO₃⁻ > SCN⁻ > Cl⁻ which can be understood in terms of a decrease in the inplane LFSE and is in accordance with the spectrochemical series. An increase in λ_{\max} on going from GBMA to E-GBHA indicates a lowering of energy with the increase in spacer carbon chain length between the two-benzimidazole groups.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the free ligand GBMA and E-GBHA shows signals for aliphatic and aromatic protons with theoretically predicted splittings (Table 1). A symmetrical multiplet in the range 7.1–7.6 ppm arises due to the benzimidazole ring protons characteristics of an AA'BB' pattern. A triplet in the range 8.5–8.9 ppm arises due to the amide NH protons (coupled to adjacent CH₂ proton). The CH₂ protons also give rise to a doublet at 4.6 ppm due to coupling with the adjacent amide NH proton. A singlet at 3.3 ppm due to the CH₂ linker (adjacent to carbonyl) for the GBMA ligand, while it appears as triplet at 2.4 ppm in case of E-GBHA. The central CH₂ linker of E-GBHA gives a quintet at 1.8 ppm. A quartet, corresponding to four protons is assigned to the CH₂ proton of the ethyl chain attached to the benzimidazole N-atom for the E-GBHA ligand. The methyl protons of the ethyl chain is found as triplet, at 1.04 ppm, coupled to neighbouring CH₂ protons.

The free ligand GBMA and E-GBHA has characteristic IR bands at 1630–1642, 1562–1548 and 1444–1470

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Analytical and spectral data of the ligands

Ligands	Analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)			¹ H NMR	UV	IR
	C	H	N	δ (ppm)	nm (log ϵ)	$\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$ (cm ⁻¹)
GBMA	57.35	5.83	21.03	8.9 (2H, t),	280 (4.32),	1630, 1562
	(57.28)	(5.52)	(21.10)	7.1–7.5 (8H, m), 4.6 (4H, d), 3.35 (2H, s)	273 (4.32)	
E-GBHA	65.50	7.21	18.43	8.5 (2H, t),	286 (3.71),	1642, 1548
	(65.30)	(7.11)	(17.58)	7.2–7.6 (8H, m), 4.6 (4H, d), 4.2 (4H, q), 2.4 (4H, t), 1.8 (4H, quin), 1.04 (6H, t)	275 (3.77)	

cm⁻¹. These are assigned to amide I ($\nu_{C=O}$ amide), ($\nu_{C=N}$)^{5a} and benzimidazole ($\nu_{C=N-C=N}$)^{5b} stretching frequencies respectively. ν_{N-H} stretching bands arise in the range 3256–3281 cm⁻¹ due to the amide NH. ν_{N-H} benzimidazole in case of GBMA arise at 3034 cm⁻¹ which is found to be missing in case of E-GBHA indicating *N*-alkylation has occurred at benzimidazole NH. On complexation a decrease in the amide I stretching frequencies and an increase in amide II stretching frequencies have been observed, which indicates the coordination of ligand through amide carbonyl oxygen. Characteristic stretching frequencies for the coordinated anions are also observed. Bands at 2100 and 800 cm⁻¹ in the thiocyanato complex ($\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{C-S}) and at 1384 cm⁻¹ due to the coordinated nitrate group (ν_{O-N-O} sym) have been observed.

EPR and cyclic voltammetry :

X-Band EPR spectra of the copper(II) complexes were recorded in DMSO at liquid nitrogen temperature. A broadening of g_{\perp} line in all of them shows that the six coordinate geometry is severely distorted through a rhombic splitting⁶. The factor $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ reflects the distortion of the equatorial plane in a six coordinate copper(II) complex. Higher the value of this factor, greater is the distortion. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ follows the order $SCN^{-} < NO_3^{-} < Cl^{-}$ for the E-GBHA series indicating that distortion in coordination geometry is least for SCN^{-} and greatest in Cl^{-} . While for GBMA complexes, the anion appears to be lost in DMSO and thus the values of g_{\parallel} and A_{\parallel} are very close to each other.

All the complexes display a quasi-reversible redox wave due to the Cu^{II}/Cu^I process. The $E_{1/2}$ values vary anodically in the order $Cl^{-} < NO_3^{-} \cong SCN^{-}$ for GBMA and E-GBHA series. When calculated against NHE, the $E_{1/2}$ values are found to be quite positive when compared with other benzimidazole⁷ and some amide based com-

plexes⁸. Upon comparison of the $E_{1/2}$ data with E-GBHA complexes it is found that the GBMA copper(II) complexes with the least spacer length between the benzimidazole amides has the most anodic $E_{1/2}$ values, implying that the ligand tends to stabilize Cu^I in preference to Cu^{II} relative to other ligand with larger number of spacer atoms.

Reactivity towards superoxide :

The cyclic voltammograms of copper(II) complexes in DMSO solution exhibit a quasi-reversible one electron redox couple in the range +0.013 to +0.088 V. The cyclic voltammogram of molecular oxygen saturated in DMSO, recorded at a glassy carbon working electrode exhibits a reversible couple at $E_{1/2}$ in the range of -1.20 to -1.45 V due to O_2/O_2^{-} redox couple⁹ (Figs. 1a, 2a). It is believed that superoxide anion is perfectly stable in the supporting electrolyte atleast on the voltammetric time scale. When the potential is scanned anodically, the Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple is unaffected indicating that neither Cu^{II} nor Cu^I is interacting with dioxygen. But in the subsequent cathodic cycle, the reversible O_2/O_2^{-} wave becomes irreversible. This irreversibility and slightly anodic shift of O_2/O_2^{-} wave indicates an interaction of superoxide anion with the copper complex. The effect is also seen on Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple where the reoxidation of Cu^I is severely inhibited (Figs. 1b, 2b). This may be explained as a result of interaction of Cu^I species with superoxide anion generated by electrochemical reduction of O_2 .

As a result of this fast reaction, all superoxide generated gets chemically reduced and is not available for electrochemical oxidation. Therefore, the reoxidation wave for O_2^{-} to O_2 is drastically decreased in height. The reactivity towards superoxide anion was monitored by varying the

Table 2. Analytical and spectral data of the copper(II) complexes

Complexes	Analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{\max} nm (log ϵ)	$E_{1/2}$ V (vs NHE)	EPR $g_{\parallel} \cdot g_{\perp}$ ($g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$) $\times 10^{-4}$	IR $\nu_{C=O}, \nu_{C=N}$ (cm^{-1})
	C	H	N				
[Cu(GBMA)Cl]Cl	46.50 (45.92)	4.19 (3.62)	16.34 (16.92)	273 (4.25), 279 (4.23), 700 (1.88)	0.66	2.26, 2.09, 136	1629, 1584
[Cu(GBMA)(NO ₃)](NO ₃)	40.24 (40.10)	4.09 (3.76)	19.60 (19.19)	273 (4.29), 279 (4.27), 670 (1.88)	0.67	2.27, 2.08, 151	1635, 1579, 1384 ($\nu_{\text{NO}_3^-}$)
[Cu(GBMA)(SCN)](SCN)	43.20 (43.63)	3.13 (3.80)	19.26 (19.39)	273 (4.16), 280 (4.13), 679 (1.74)	0.67	2.09	1655, 1532, 2112 (ν_{SCN^-})
[Cu(E-GBHA)Cl]Cl	48.30 (48.51)	4.62 (5.94)	13.20 (12.81)	278 (4.35), 286 (4.32), 898 (1.98)	0.61	2.39, 2.08, 170	1635, 1579
[Cu(E-GBHA)NO ₃](NO ₃)	48.00 (47.92)	5.94 (5.12)	16.19 (16.88)	278 (4.20), 286 (4.18), 822 (1.53)	0.64	2.39, 2.09, 161	1614, 1562, 1383 ($\nu_{\text{NO}_3^-}$)
[Cu(E-GBHA)SCN](SCN)	51.50 (50.77)	4.51 (5.14)	16.17 (16.62)	278 (4.26), 286 (4.22), 827 (1.85)	0.63	2.37, 2.08, 148	1656, 1519, 2106 (ν_{SCN^-})

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of DMSO solution containing 0.1 M $\text{Bu}_4\text{N}(\text{ClO}_4)$: (a) saturated with oxygen, (b) containing 0.9 mM (final concentration) $[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{GBMA})]$ at a scan rate of 100 mV/s.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of DMSO solution containing 0.1 M $\text{Bu}_4\text{N}(\text{ClO}_4)$: (a) saturated with oxygen, (b) containing 0.525 mM (final concentration) $[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{EGBHA})]$ at a scan rate of 100 mV/s.

Fig. 3. Plot of anodic peak current (μA) vs conc. of $[CuCl_2(GBMA)]$.

Fig. 4. Plot of anodic peak current (μA) vs conc. of $[CuCl_2(E-GBHA)]$.

concentration of copper(II) complexes starting from a concentration of $O_2 : Cu^{II}$ complex as 18 : 1. One fold complex is added each time and the total drop in current value (both cathodic and anodic) was measured. Care was taken not to expose the solution to air.

At all potentials beyond +0.010 V, $[CuL]^{2+}$ complex is present in reduced form $[(CuL)^+]$. The Cu^I reacts with superoxide generated electrochemically to form peroxide O_2^{2-} and oxidized complex $[(CuL)]^{2+}$. The oxidized complex is perhaps similar to original copper(II) complex and can again be electrochemically reduced to Cu^I complex $[(CuL)^+]$ which is equally effective in quenching the superoxide ion. The cycle has thus been repeated to yield back the oxidized complex, $[(CuL)]^{2+}$ and peroxide ion. At this stage some structural changes arise in the oxidized complex, making it ineffective to carry out the cycle further. Thus the cycle does not proceed beyond two steps

and for each mole of copper(II) complex of E-GBHA added, two moles of oxygen are consumed.

Experimental

Materials : Glycinebenzimidazole dihydrochloride was prepared by following the procedure reported by Cescon and Day¹⁰. Spectroscopic grade solvents were employed for oxygenation experiments. All other chemicals were obtained from commercial sources and were used as received.

Physical measurements : Elemental analyses were obtained from the micro analytical laboratory of RSIC, Chandigarh, India. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in the solid state as KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer FTIR-2000 spectrometer. EPR data were recorded on a X-band Varian E-112 spectrometer with a variable temperature liquid Nitrogen Cryostat at IIT, Mumbai, India. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker-Spin instrument. Cyclic voltammograms of all the complexes were recorded in 2 : 8 DMSO : CH₃CN solution with 0.1 M TBAP⁺ as supporting electrolyte. A three-electrode configuration composed of Pt disk working electrode, a Pt wire counter electrode and a Ag/AgNO₃ reference electrode was used. The electrochemical studies on superoxide were carried out in DMSO, with glassy carbon as working electrode.

Synthesis of ligands : *N,N'*-Bis(2-benzimidazolylmethyl)propane diamide (GBMA) :

The ligand was prepared following the procedure reported by Gupta *et al.*¹¹. The ligand was recrystallized with MeOH : H₂O mixture (1 : 1). Yield : 1.8 g, m.p. 240°C.

N,N'-Bis(*N*-ethyl-2-benzimidazolylmethyl)hexane diamide (E-GBHA) :

This ligand was synthesized by procedure reported by Tehlan *et al.*¹². The ligand was recrystallized with hot methanol. Yield : 280 mg, m.p. 192°C.

Synthesis of the complexes : $[Cu(GBMA)Cl_2]$: To a methanolic solution of the ligand (GBMA) 0.5 mmol was added to a green solution of $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ in methanol (0.5 mmol). Upon mixing the color of the solution changed to bluish-green and a blue complex started to appear within a few minutes of stirring. The mixture was allowed to stir for another 30 min. The product obtained was then centrifuged, washed with methanol 2-3 times and air-dried. Yield : 150 mg (60.4%).

$[Cu(E-GBHA)Cl_2]$: The above complex of ligand E-

GBHA was synthesized in a manner similar to that reported for chloride complex of the ligand GBMA. The dark green colored compound obtained was washed with methanol 2-3 times and air-dried. Yield 185 mg (62.3%).

[Cu(GBMA)(NO₃)₂] : This complex was prepared in the same manner as that described for the chloride complex, by taking CuNO₃·3H₂O in place of CuCl₂·2H₂O. The color changed to dark blue on mixing and a deep blue colored complex started to appear within 5 min of stirring. This was further stirred for next 30 min. Product was centrifuged and washed with methanol 2-3 times. Complex so obtained was air-dried. Yield : 160 mg (58.2%).

[Cu(E-GBHA)(NO₃)₂] : A light green complex was obtained after following the above procedure by taking the ligand, E-GBHA in place of the ligand GBMA. Yield : 150 mg (46.3%).

[Cu(GBMA)(SCN)₂] : A methanolic solution of KSCN was added drop wise to a solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O (0.5 mmol) in methanol. The resulting brown solution was centrifuged and KCl formed was rejected. The clear brown solution was then added to the solution of GBMA (0.5 mmol). Immediate precipitation of green product was observed. The complex was filtered off, washed with methanol and air-dried. Yield : 120 mg (44.3%).

[Cu(E-GBHA)(SCN)₂] : This was synthesized by a method similar to that adopted for the synthesis of above complex by taking E-GBHA instead of GBMA. A dirty green complex was obtained, washed with methanol and air-dried. Yield : 240 mg (82.5%).

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